

The Collision of Politics and Administrative Dichotomy in Implementing the National Development Plan: A Perspective on South Africa's Local Government

Maela Khutso Delphus, Takalani Hulisani, and Maemu Emmanuel

Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

The political-administrative dichotomy conceptualises the separation of political and administrative execution and decision-making within governmental systems. Theoretically, this concept entails that elected officials (politicians) set policies, goals, and objectives, while appointed civil servants (administrators) carry out these directives without being influenced by political considerations. It aims to prevent the politicisation of bureaucratic processes, ensuring that decisions are made based on merit, expertise, and adherence to established laws and regulations rather than political agendas. However, in practice, the difficulty in separating politics and administration results in problems like partisan appointments, administrative favouritism, bureaucratic inefficiencies, competing agendas, erosion of administrative independence, and others, posing various threats to local government administration. This paper probes the impact of the collision of administrative and political dichotomy in implementing the National Development Plan (NDP) 2023 in South African municipalities. The study relies on secondary data wherein available literature was used to supplement projected arguments. Theoretically, the paper uses the Political Bureaucratic model. The paper finds that reducing the tension between political and administrative interests allows municipalities to better align their actions with the objectives of the NDP 2030 and deliver more sustainable and effective outcomes. This paper argues that the collision of administrative and political dichotomy negatively affects local governments' ability to meet their NDP targets and objectives. The paper recommends that there is a clear separation of the two functions to ensure neutrality, efficiency, and professionalism in NDP implementation. The paper also recommends the strengthening of the institutional frameworks that guarantee the autonomy of administrative entities, augment transparency and responsibility in the process of decision-making, and cultivate an environment that prioritises evidence-based policymaking. This paper seeks to stimulate further research interest in the anatomy of municipalities as key government structures that works to advance national programmes such as the NDP 2030.

Keywords: politics, administrators, political-administrative dichotomy, national development plan

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa of 1996 clearly outlines the roles, functions, and responsibilities of both government administrators and politicians in governing and administering the country effectively and efficiently. Malobela (2023:162) articulates that the South African local government has seen significant political and administrative reform and transition since the democratic dispensation of 1994. Yawa (2016) and Thornhill (2020) allude that one of the major problems for municipalities to deal with is the idea of the politics-administrative dichotomy. Chgwata (2023) concurs that service delivery backlogs have been caused by the dysfunctional

politics-administrative interface in South Africa's local government. In reality, it is difficult to distinguish between the duties and obligations of politicians and administrators since officials may start to compete with one another in political contests and hierarchical structures. Fraser (2023) argues that although administration and politics are separated by the constitution, power struggles frequently occur.

Since municipalities in South Africa struggle to resolve the relationship between administrators and politicians, Mngomezulu (2020) claims that political interference in the implementation of service delivery is a major issue in many of these municipalities. In addition, Mngomezulu (2020) notes that there appears to be unwarranted political intervention in organizational issues and a tense relationship between administrative and political authorities in local government. Local governments are tiers of government that coordinate local initiatives with national policies and local service delivery. According to Pretorius (2017:1), local government encompasses the exchanges that occur between holders of administrative and political offices when decisions are made locally. According to Jacobsen (2001:5), because local government plays such a significant role in public administration, these relationships, whether emphasised by ideological contestation of the classical administration-politics dichotomy, have theoretical and practical resonance in the Public Administration discourse. According to Guo (2019), the political-administrative dichotomy is a key component

Author Note

Maela Khutso Delphus, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

E-mail: khutso.maela@univen.ac.za

Takalani Hulisani, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

Maemu Emmanuel, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

E-mail: emmanuel.maemu@univen.ac.za

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to

Takalani Hulisani, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

E-mail: hulisani.takalani@univen.ac.za

of public administration and is intimately tied to the field's identity. It also has a significant impact on the field's practice.

The NDP 2030 calls for effective government leadership as well as cooperation from all facets of society. Social and economic transformation in a society with significant social and economic divides is impossible without a capable and developing state. The state provides the institutions and infrastructure required for the economy and society to function. It is imperative that significant steps be taken to establish a state capable of realizing the 2030 vision. Even in a capable or developing state, political and administrative dichotomy is still a problem. Consequently, to achieve the state's NDP 2030, the obstacles resulting from the political and administrative dichotomy must be attended to or addressed.

This paper argues that the separation of political decision-making and administrative implementation within governmental structures is fundamental for achieving the NDP. While recognizing that the practical separation of the two may be difficult because of the blurred lines, tensions, and conflicts between administrators and political office bearers, the paper acknowledges that this division is important for ensuring impartiality, accountability, and government efficiency.

Conceptualisation of Terms

Political-administrative Dichotomy

Public administration frequently engages in contentious discussions regarding the intersection of politics and administration. The discussions around the administrative vs political dichotomy, according to Young et al. (2020:483), stem from the understanding that all public employees have determinative influences and can their actions may significantly affect public service primacies. Thus, their job is to strike a crucial balance between political leadership and democratic demands. According to McCandless and Guy (2013:356-357), Woodrow's 1887 classical theorization of the politics-public dichotomy served as the catalyst for years of discussion on the topic, including the separation between political and local government administration. According to Woodrow (1887:210), "although politics sets the administration tasks, it should not be suffered to manipulate its offices." Moreover, the writers have explored various strands, such as "a separation between partisan politics and efficient municipal administration." Grant (2014) asserts that the administrative and political spheres have different mandates regarding matters of governance and are therefore distinct from one another. However, an analysis of recent and prior research indicates that politics and administration are constantly interacting (McCandless & Guy, 2013: 357). Despite numerous national efforts to stabilise the interface between politics and administration in South Africa, including those undertaken by the NDP 2030, Chigova and Hofisi (2023:193) assert that there are still developing issues in this area. The National Planning Commission (NPC), which is in charge of overseeing the NDP's implementation, recommends the creation of a professionalized public service that seeks to serve the government while also being sufficiently autonomous and free from political patronage. The demand is for a clearer separation of duties between political leaders.

Political Interference

Political interference, in the opinion of Stocker and Thompson-

Fawcett (2014:806) becomes the rule rather than the exception in the public sector when there is a blurring of the roles played by political and administrative officeholders. The Municipal Councillors' Code of Conduct prohibits this kind of interference. Council members are specifically prohibited from taking part in tender decision-making procedures by Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) Section 118. Despite this, Mhelembe and Mafini (2019) contend that municipalities continue to face significant challenges related to the political-administrative interface, particularly regarding tender processes. According to Mbandlwa et al. (2020: 1648), the efficacy and efficiency of service delivery are impacted by the interference of local political leadership in public administration and a lack of ethics. Furthermore, the writers contend that municipalities are frequently seen as the most impacted government institutions since numerous officials and council members have been found to participate in corrupt activities, and some of them directly interfere in the day-to-day operations of various municipal apparatuses (Mbandlwa et al., 2020:1649).

Corruption

Sebake (2020:168-169) claims that corruption is a complicated phenomenon, and Chapter 2 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, which upholds the provision of citizens' rights, should be used to contextualise corruption's complexity and effects on humanity. The government services restore certain rights. In this case, the story of corruption calls into question the ability of the state to carry out its constitutional mandate and duties. Mahlala and Netswera (2020:482) hold the opinion that corruption is defined as the actions or conduct of those in positions of authority in public office that go against their responsibilities as public servants and are motivated by the desire to obtain unjustified personal or other gratification. They also point out that corrupt practices are widespread in South African society and are thought to be particularly prevalent in the areas of local government, interactions between citizens and traffic officials, and state-owned enterprises. Municipal corruption includes the misappropriation of funds, the unlawful transfer of funds, favouritism in the procurement process, bribery, corrupt travel reimbursements, the creation of fictitious tenders, non-payment for municipal services by members of the council, the use of municipal resources for political party activities, the recruiting of general staff members without advertising, and other irregularities (Thuli & Selepe, 2023:691). Hlongwane (2015) argues that corruption and fraud in all spheres of government are signs of problems with governance.

National Development Plan

According to the government of South Africa (2013), the NDP has functioned as a roadmap providing a long-term outlook for the objectives the country aspires to accomplish. The NDP aims to alleviate extreme poverty and lower the country's inequality by 2030. The NDP's primary function is to provide a long-term action plan for achieving these goals. The goal of the NDP policy, according to the NPC (2019), is to ensure South Africans' future as outlined in the Constitution (van Wyk, 2020: 354). Hendrickse (2024:225) citing Enaifoghe (2019: 120) traces the NDP's genesis to the Accelerated and Shared Growth Initiative for South Africa (ASGISA). It was replaced by, the New Growth Path (NGP) in 2010. The author claims that the NGP was created to address issues of unemployment and poverty as well as to hasten South Africa's

economic development. In 2023, the NGP was superseded by the NDP, which served as a model for the nation's future financial and economic development strategy.

Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, this paper employs the adversarial model first conceptualised by Peters (1987) as a framework to study politico-administrative relations. Hulst et al. (2015) posit that the adversarial model characterises how politicians and administrators are in a constant battle to maintain control of public administration and authority over policy processes rather than to focus on their collaboration. This view is based on the notion that both parties are driven by desires to achieve their separate goals such as personal benefits, and electoral dominance or political power. Carboni (2010:90) also concedes that there is a permanent battle for power between administrators and politicians which is characterised by overlapping roles between the two parties. Redish and Hiltner (2023:487) posit that liberal adversary democracy accommodates conflict rather than looking to eliminate it; it also depends on individual interests as the driver of political processes while accepting that factions, dissent, and disagreements are inevitable and can also be crucial in protecting individual liberties. This paper therefore used the adversarial model to determine the constant struggle between public office bearers and politicians in implementing the NDP targets from a local government perspective.

Method

A review of the literature was used to source the data, and a desktop qualitative approach was chosen. According to Leavy (2014), inductive approaches to knowledge-building are used in qualitative research in order to generate meaning. Thus, the researcher employed this methodology to thoroughly examine and gain knowledge of the administrative and political dichotomy phenomena found in South Africa's local government structure. A literature review assesses the current level of knowledge regarding a specific subject. Examples of its applications include developing research agendas, identifying research gaps, and simply having a conversation about a specific topic (Snyder, 2019:334). Using published journals, books, statutory reports, and documents produced by government agencies, this study investigated how the conflict between political and administrative responsibilities continues to exist and potentially impacts the effectiveness and operation of different South African municipalities.

Contextualization of Political-administrative Dichotomy in SA's Local Government

According to the PSC (2024), Chapter 13 of the NDP identified the following key reforms in line with a commitment to building a capable state: stabilize political and administrative relations; make careers in public service and local government administration appealing; enhance technical skills; improve accountability, delegation, and oversight; as well as departmental coordination; take a proactive approach to improve relations between all branches of government; and provide clarity on how to govern State-Owned entities. Vilakazi and Adetiba (2020) asserted that the administrative and political dichotomy is conceptualised to explain both political and administrative domains' collaboration and their distinguishability in the public service or government. This theory's central claim is

that, in public management, the political and administrative domains should have equal authority and responsibility without interfering with one another's purview. Furthermore, they view South Africa as susceptible to the collision of administrative and political dichotomy, as it has been persistently identified as an issue in the global public administration field. It has been extremely difficult to distinguish between political and administrative responsibilities in municipalities, especially when one takes into account how municipal systems function.

The politicization of municipal administrative components, according to Masuku and Jili (2019), is the reason behind the poor governance and service delivery at the local government level. This is also demonstrated by the fact that political ties play a crucial role in how public institutions operate, which in turn affects choices about hiring government officials. Conversely, Napier (2018) argued that the public sector, particularly local government, has generally ignored the separation of powers. The political bureaucratic paradigm states that the public service must be supervised and governed by elected office-bearers. This suggests that administration and politics, as well as party and state, are synonymous. Koma and Modumo (2016) contend that since municipal services should be provided equitably and not just to those with political agendas, administrative components of local government should maintain their political neutrality. Heywood (1997: 335) asserts that politicians are thought to be controlled when they are appointed to high bureaucratic positions like general management and senior management. Politicians have the authority to dictate how bureaucracy in the public sector functions as emphasised by Mafunisa (2003) who said that the politicised bureaucratic model does just that. In the politicized bureaucratic paradigm, politicians hold a dominant position and oversee government functions. Tshishonga (2014) asserts that the basis of the politicized model in South Africa is the African National Congress (ANC) cadre policy and development strategy, which was developed in 1997 and places a strong emphasis on internal recruitment. Prospective members are also instructed in the party's core policies and programs by the ANC. Since the municipal council chooses who gets hired, political influence impairs the performance of municipal officials within municipalities. Though the local political party has a say in candidate selection, municipal managers are selected by a majority vote of the municipal council.

Discussion of Findings: Impacts of Politics Versus Administrative Collision on NDP Implementation In Municipalities

Cadre Deployment

The NDP in South Africa is failing for a number of reasons, according to Ukwandu (2019), cited in Pietersen (2023:471). These include a lack of political will that goes beyond rhetoric, a shortage of critical skills in the public sector (such as engineers at the local government level), irrelevant policies, cadre deployment the exact opposite of meritocracy and the use of SoEs for grand corruption and political patronage. Shava and Chamisa (2018) claim that the deployment of cadres made problems with corruption, inefficient procurement practices, wasteful spending, and the deteriorating condition of local government worse. Selepe (2023:183) further argues that the growing number of politically connected people

employed by local governments and other public organisations has exacerbated corruption in government and has become a threat to achieving the aims and objectives of a developmental state across the board. Mngomezulu (2020) claims that the ANC's cadre deployment strategy, which maintains the idea that applicants should be selected for positions based on their length of service and commitment to the organization, hurts service delivery because it hires unqualified and incompetent employees who perform their jobs poorly. According to Sithomola (2019:72), cadre deployment is a result of a lack of leadership and is a component of the subversion of the Republic's legal and policy framework. As such, this phenomenon does not correspond with the Republic's legislative and policy framework. It results in a leadership vacuum that encourages corruption by tearing down governance structures, replacing them with chaos and misrule, and enacting arbitrary laws and directives that lack checks and balances. Despite several interventions and legislative frameworks like the Public Service Act, this issue has persisted to be a significant one for municipalities as well as the larger state apparatus. In their argument, Klaaren, Brunette, and Belvedere (2022:24) contend that the Public Service Act fails to adequately monitor and balance political office bearers when it comes to appointing and removing individuals from the broader public service. Instead, they propose that the PSC, given appropriate independence and authority, can act as this watchdog through a number of elaborations based on the NDP, which is formally government policy and is primarily concerned with protecting public administrations from illegal political interference.

Political Interference

According to Campos and Reich (2019:224), political interference is when elected officials meddle in internal affairs with the intention of advancing their own or their party's interests. The authors also make note of the fact that all areas of government have policy frameworks that direct the interactions between administrators and legislators. Phago (2020) demonstrates that political meddling in municipal administrative governance has unfavorable effects and is thus against municipal policies. The author draws attention to the fact that nearly 31% of South African municipalities lack financial sustainability and attributes this problem to various elements, such as political meddling and internal strife within municipal councils. Furthermore, because council members who meddle in municipal procurement procedures are not held accountable to the municipal council and Municipal Public Accounts Committee (MPAC), the author argues that political interference is a problem that undermines accountability measures and prevents effective municipal planning and implementation by municipal administrative officials (Phago, 2020:185-188). According to Matheus et al. (2020:101), political meddling has caused corruption and muddied the lines of accountability. Anafo et al. (2021:5) citing the challenges associated with the COVID-19 response, attest that certain municipalities were unable to manage the pandemic effectively because they were not meeting their developmental agenda. The author continued by saying that towns did not supply the hygienic conditions and clean water needed to control the COVID-19 outbreak.

Bureaucratic Inefficiencies

The NDP 2030, regarded as the most extensive and extensively consulted government plan to date, is not without implementation

challenges, according to van Wyk and Coetzee (2022: 140141). These include the generally subpar and uneven quality of services and related corruption in state entities, which is bolstered by the public's growing perception of ongoing government incompetence. Moreover, they assert that there exist additional variables associated with difficulties in executing public policies that pertain to the proficiency and abilities of public employees. This includes the small pool of qualified candidates to fill open positions, which results in instability in important roles, as well as the lack of necessary competencies, as noted by the PFMA Report (2017/18:51). The NDP, according to Mlambo (2023:14-15), is an essential document that aims to provide South Africa with a roadmap for eradicating poverty and reducing inequality, among other things. Additionally, it highlights important issues that need to be resolved in each of the three areas of government to achieve this: The authors contend that this shows that the ANC and the NDP are cognizant of the problems facing the public sector, especially concerning local government, where corruption and subpar service delivery are pervasive.

Ndevu and Muller (2018:187) note that the NDP 2030 acknowledges in its chapter on local government that issues resulting from poor decision-making, political appointments, and party-political interventions have affected public servant morale and citizens' trust in government entities including municipalities. Matloga (2023:52) makes the case, citing Van Wyk (2020) that the NDP at local government is difficult to implement because many of these entities are currently unable to offer services to the community. The NDP also advances slowly due to ongoing economic strain, rising rates of unemployment, inequality, and corruption in both the private and public sectors alike. To comprehend this, one must consider the overall situation of South Africa's local government. According to Masiya et al. (2021:102), it is challenging to enhance municipal service delivery in South Africa due to the legacy of apartheid government policies mainly because public infrastructure of that time was not designed with inclusivity in mind. This is true even though the government has set commendable goals to raise the calibre of services rendered at the local level; consequently, the public's expectations and fundamental standards are not satisfied.

Competing Political Agendas

According to Khambule (2021:513), only a capacitated and incorruptible bureaucracy led by political leadership focused on development can give rise to a capable, ethical, and developing state. Considering that South Africa has a participatory system, the NDP suggested enhancing oversight and accountability measures to make sure public servants and political leaders take responsibility for the provision of services, as stated by the NPC (2012). The situation at local government is however characterised by political tensions and competing agendas that derail from their developmental path as evidenced by the chaos and instability that comes with coalition governments. Coalition local governments are not new to South African local politics; however, from 2016 to 2021, they gained prominence following the decline in ANC support in several major metropolises, including Tshwane, Johannesburg, and Nelson Mandela Bay. Numerous political challenges followed these coalitions. For instance, internal fighting among coalition partners shook the Nelson Mandela Bay Municipality, which ultimately resulted in the recall of DA mayor Athol Trollip (Khambule, 2023:168). According to Munzhedzi and Shopola (2024: 25), there

is frequently a lack of trust among political leaders, which causes friction between them even though coalition governments require that leaders of such parties or coalitions collaborate regularly. This is because party leaders do not believe that leaders of other political parties will put forward the interests of the coalition governments and communities before their party interests. To illustrate their point, the authors cited the mid-2019 breakdown of the DA and EFF's working relationship as a result of mistrust, with the DA stating that they would not cede the mayoral seat of Tshwane Metro to the EFF. According to Duvenhage (2023:200), "political opportunism" is one of the fundamental causes of coalition local government failures, as parties and individual party leaders form alliances for their partisan advantage rather than the benefit of the local community as a whole. Mokgosi and Shai (2017: 5354) contend that the caustic behaviour within political parties can be used to understand the corrosive behaviour within municipalities because political parties are breeding grounds for institutional and political cultures that are compatible with democratic institutions. Municipalities have disproportionately reproduced political party disobedience to organisational cultures and democratic principles. The delivery of essential services, which the municipalities support, has faced significant obstacles as a result of this development, particularly in those municipalities that were previously run by a single party but now need a coalition to be governed.

Erosion of Administrative Independence

It is concerning, according to Masuku and Jili (2019:6), that even the NDP was created to deal with problems that originate in municipalities. The authors cite the NDP (2013) in pointing out that a variety of intricate factors, such as conflicts in the political-administrative nexus, have produced unpredictable capacity, which in turn results in unpredictable performance in local, provincial, and federal governments. This is one of the implementation challenges facing the plan. To counteract this, the authors propose that public service be integrated into the development agenda while being shielded from excessive political meddling. Although it is ideal to separate administrative and political decisions, Mlambo et al. (2022-213) acknowledge that this is highly unlikely to happen in developing countries because politics and the public sector are so closely entwined. The practice of deploying political cadres to advance party interests has drawn criticism, predominantly because of the worsening quality of public service. Rather, the authors contend that the public sector's incapacity to keep politics and administrative decisions apart has led to impunity, increased cronyism, and low levels of accountability, undermining societal needs.

According to research by Mngomezulu (2020:43), this is a pressing problem that many South Africans face, leading many communities to demonstrate in support of prompt or sufficient service delivery. The study found that the division of the executive and legislative powers help the municipalities to effectively manage the delivery of service; however, there are indications, as some respondents pointed out, that the local government system needs to be reviewed overall because, occasionally, it is not conducive to address public needs and the delivery of services may favour certain wards. Additionally, participants urged the division of the executive and legislative branches because it reduces the potential for intervention. Interestingly, there is another point of view that contends that communities will benefit from partnership between the

administrative and political branches of government rather than from their separation. According to Vilakazi and Adetiba (2020), this viewpoint is also positively viewed by the local government sector because the collaboration of administrative and political domains is essential for the effective functioning of municipalities. Additionally, the authors caution quoting Mdlongwa (2014) that office-bearers and senior officials from both spheres are equally responsible for malevolent performances, and political meddling in municipalities is unfairly blamed (Vilakazi & Adetiba, 2020:49-57). This perspective therefore implies that the dysfunction in certain municipalities can be attributed to both the political and administrative domains.

Recommendations

This paper makes the following recommendations for how South Africa's local governments should better align their operations with the NDP 2030, which will lessen conflict and improve overall governance and service delivery.

- To maintain administrative stability and coherence, municipalities should implement the law and code of discipline more consistently, irrespective of the political party in power. Legislation should be amended to precisely define the functions and duties of administrative and political offices. Municipalities should regularly audit and assess local government operations to ensure compliance with policies and procedures
- There should be ongoing training (workshops & capacity-building initiatives) to increase sound comprehension of the laws and regulations, as well as guidelines to boost knowledge about the distinction between administrative and legislative power in municipalities.
- The Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs should enforce a merit-based recruitment process for administrators and other top officials, rather than favouring party allegiance. This will guarantee the recruitment of the most qualified individuals for local government.
- A revision to the current legislation or laws is desperately needed to clearly define the separation of powers between legislators and administrators in local government. This revision must consider both the realities of everyday life and the fact that difficulties persist despite the current laws and regulations.
- Create independent oversight committees to keep an eye on compliance and handle conflicts of interest. Moreover, establish and uphold whistle blower protection laws to promote the reporting of wrongdoing without fear of reprisal.

Conclusion

This paper focused on the collision of politics and administrative dichotomy in implementing the National Development Plan (NDP). Using a desktop qualitative methodology, the study collected data from books, statutory reports, published articles, and documents from government agencies. The study found that carrying out official duties is often ambiguous, even though there are some guidelines to distinguish between political and administrative functions. Political influence over administrative duties therefore has serious ramifications for the already poor and compromised delivery of municipal services. In the end, this has hampered the national government's attempts to carry out the NDP successfully. The paper makes the recommendation that, regardless of the

political party in power, municipalities should enforce laws and codes of discipline more consistently in order to maintain administrative stability and coherence. When necessary, laws about local government operations should be amended. This will help to explicitly define administrative and legislative roles and functions. Regular audits and evaluations of these operations are also necessary to ensure that policies and procedures are being followed.

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